

PROFESSIONAL MOBILITY AND SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT

Zokirjon Muminov

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in sociology. Director of the
Center for R and ATMTSES at Namangan State University

E-mail: zokir_odiliy@mail.ru

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ABSTRACT.

The article talks about professional mobility, which is considered relevant in our society. The importance of the formation and development of professional mobility among young people is emphasized. Opinions are given on the importance of professional mobility in this process. It is emphasized that the focus on acquiring a profession in Uzbekistan is inherited from our ancestors, the phenomenon of professional migration is one of the little-studied areas, especially among young people, the issue of developing professional skills and innovative thinking is being discussed.

Key words: professional intellectual potential, professional skills, labor migration, intellectual migration, migration processes, internal migration and professional mobility, exchange of places between generations, decent living in public life.

INTRODUCTION.

In the world, issues of institutionalization of professional mobility in internal migration processes on the basis of professional requirements are being approached as a factor of social phenomenon. It remains an important priority task for migrants to move from one area to another in order to not only make a living, but also to show their potential. Scientific research based on the study of not only the employment of migrants in the globalized world, but also their socio-psychological mood, application of theoretical methodological concepts and empirical methods to the problem, classification of the transformation of the institutionalization of migrant mobility, sociological measurement and forecasting of dynamic development indicators is gaining urgent importance.

In the framework of practical sociological research in the Republic of Uzbekistan, in addition to the study of problems such as "professional intellectual potential", "professional skills", "labor migration", "intellectual migration", "migration processes", "internal migration" and "professional mobility" " issues have been researched in one way or another from today's point of view as a social problem. In the changing times, it is important for

generations to change places, to have their place in society, and to ensure that they live a decent life in social life.

Literature analysis and methodology.

In the Action Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "creating conditions for the full implementation of labor and entrepreneurial activity of the able-bodied population, improving the quality of the workforce, expanding the system of vocational training, retraining and upgrading of skills of persons in need of employment"[1] The paragraph called is relevant as an important methodological source in our research work. Historical, ethnocultural, philosophical aspects of social mobility are analyzed in the works of classic thinkers such as Farobi, Beruni, Mirzo Ulugbek. For example, in Beruni's work "Monuments from Ancient Nations", it can be seen that "in the five-thousand-year history of nations, the dynastic aspects of governance were compared with territorial indicators [2]. Also, classifications related to the profession related to social communities are given in Alisher Navoi's "Mahbub-ul Qulub"[3], "Majolisun Nafois"[4] and other works.

General aspects of internal migration have been studied by Uzbek scientists. In particular, in the study of internal migration, the study of professional mobility, especially the approach to it based on territorial characteristics, and the state of relations has become an urgent task of sociology. M. Bekmurodov, [5] R. Ubaydullaeva, B. Umurzokov, L. Maksakova, M. Ganieva, G. Abdurahmonova, D. Rasulova, O. Ata-Mirzaev, A. Umarov, A. Kholbekov, A. Qakharov, K. Kalanov, Sh. Isakulov, Sh. Sodikova, A. Seitov, F. Parmanov, M. Gafforova conducted effective research.

According to the researcher A.V.Kiryakova, studying the professional training of a person and forming a system of universal and professional values, which determines his attitude to the world and environmental activities, to himself, is the direction of vocational education. should be paid attention to. Then I present myself as a person and a professional[8]. Value relations occupy an important place in axiology, and it is understood as the process of managing mobile individuals engaged in the selection, evaluation and research of values. Value orientations mean the result of management of professional processes related to inclusion of existing values in personal characteristics and directing them to practical activities[9]

In professional mobility, Z.A.Damchenko paid special attention to the formation of valuable relations related to the activity of a specialist and emphasized that values-goals, values-means, values-attitude, values-quality and valuable knowledge should be distinguished.

Another theoretical-methodological feature of professional mobility is the "activity-based approach". Activity is considered as the basis, means and condition for the development of personal characteristics, changing the model of the surrounding reality in accordance with the purpose. When determining the tasks of professional mobility, it is understood the selection and organization of personal activities from the point of view of the subject of labor and communication knowledge. This includes awareness, goal setting, activity planning, organization, evaluation of results, and self-analysis (reflection).

The approach of personal activity means identifying active methods and forms of organizing the professional process, contributing to activity and self-development, which help to distinguish the characteristics of personal mobility, serve to develop his professional mobility. This methodological approach determines the basis of individual aspects in the development of a person's professional mobility. In sociology, internal (related to personal and professional development, readiness to master new methods, technologies, forms of professional activity) and external (position, profession, workplace, professional training related to change) forms of professional mobility differ. Active consideration of the problem of professional mobility in professional specialization began in the 70s of the 20th century.

Results.

The current situation in the labor market, the increase in requirements for the qualifications of a mobile person, the phenomenon of standardization and activation of professional activity have created the need for the formation of

qualities such as personal professional mobility. In sociological literature, vertical and horizontal professional mobility of a specialist is distinguished. The first one is mainly related to status growth, while the second one is distinguished by the realization of the employee's ability to perform effective professional activity in the conditions of changing labor realities.

- an internal migrant is an ethnic and cultural-historical meaning that is permanently or temporarily mobile, is a citizen of one or another country, can speak the state language, and is based on the territorial location of the country in which he resides. is a person with information;

- professional mobility is a state of clear activation of human thinking in short periods of time, which ensures that a person acquires new knowledge, intellectual skills and skills at a high speed. Also, professional potential does not guarantee the efficiency of the work of workers without special education or professional experience;

- any professional mobility in the society is important as a real force driving the social management system. In the information society, the role of professional skills began to serve as a foundation for many fields. Nevertheless, the influence of the sociological approach in scientific researches is less noticeable. When analyzing scientific sources and research works, it became known that researches were conducted in one way or another in the fields of philosophy, psychology, and management. This places serious demands on sociology;

-In the 21st century, internal migration has become an important characteristic of the object of social management. In recent years, the diagnosis of internal migration has become the object of multidisciplinary research in scientific management. Professional mobility of a person is a multidisciplinary research object and has formed the world of cognitive paradigms. In this, the science of "cognitology" was formed from the achievements of the sciences of sociology, linguistics, cybernetics, logic, and psychology as a main direction and developed as an interdisciplinary complex science network.

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